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A sonication-assisted method for the production of true-to-life nanoplastics from polymeric materials

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Abstract

Worldwide plastic production has surpassed four hundred megatons over the last two years, this trend steadily rising and making plastic become one of the more serious environmental pollutants. While a wide knowledge is already existing about macroplastics, a recent and complex problem to tackle is degradation of these materials to micro- and nanoplastics. It has been demonstrated that organisms react in a different way to naturally degraded nanoplastics (NPs) when compared with NPs produced in the laboratory, the artificially created ones being more widely reported in research studies. As a consequence, new approaches need to be orientated towards NP release mimicking particles produced in the environment. The objective of this study is to develop and optimize a sonication-assisted method for degrading macroplastics and generating NPs from different real-life polymeric sources. Specimens of use were tire treads, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles, high-density polystyrene (HDPS) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE). Special attention was paid to lessening the workload in the laboratory and minimising both contamination and thermal degradation. Every plastic-based item was cryogenically milled, and small amounts of the resulting powder were suspended in water and subjected to ultrasound treatment in a bath with an applied ultrasonic energy density of 7.0 kJ ml^{-1} (equivalent to 64 h of sonication at 160 W). Particle sizing was primarily performed with dynamic light scattering. Whereas LDPE showed a little sign of nanoparticle production, possibly due to energy input, PET and tyres released quantifiable amounts of nanoparticles after receiving 5.2 kJ ml^{-1} (equivalent to 48 h of sonication at 160 W) of ultrasonic energy density. Hydrodynamic diameters varied from 150 up to 300 nm for these two polymers. It was hypothesised that additives may prevent degradation to a certain extent, thus highlighting the necessity for increasing the total applied ultrasonic energy to promote plastic degradation.

1. Introduction

Plastics have become one of the most widely used materials over the past century, primarily due to their versatility and low cost. Polypropylene (PP), low density polyethylene (LDPE), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyurethane (PUR) and polystyrene (PS) comprise almost 77% of the produced plastic worldwide [1]. The global demand for plastics has quadrupled over the past four decades and is expected to continue rising in the future [2, 3], thereby exacerbating the impact on the environment and human health. The massive production of these materials has led to their pervasive presence and accumulation in nearly all ecosystems [4, 5].

Despite being considered durable, plastics are continuously exposed to dynamic environmental conditions, such as those found in the ocean, making them susceptible to degradation through abiotic mechanisms. Factors such as thermal and photo degradation, as well as mechanical abrasion, contribute to this process. Plastic

degradation into smaller pieces gives rise to microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs). MPs are defined as larger than 1 μm (1000 nm) but smaller than 5 mm [6], and NPs are generally classified as colloidal particles with a size in the range 1–1000 nm [7]. Recent studies have confirmed the presence of MPs and NPs in coastal areas, sediments, and water columns [8, 9].

There are two types of NPs that can be found in nature. Firstly, there are synthetic bottom-up NPs, already prepared for this size. These NPs are uniform in size and shape and mostly found in cosmetics and personal care products. Until recently they were used in investigating the impact of NP on the environment and living organisms. Secondly, there are top-down NPs, also referred to true-to-life NPs if prepared in the laboratory by mechanical and physicochemical methods [10]. These NPs are produced when macroplastics start to degrade not uniformly, with inconsistent both size and shape. However, studies have already shown that human plasma reacts differently to top-down in relation to bottom-up produced NPs [11–13].

While both types of NPs are expected to be found in nature, only top-down particles have been discovered [14, 15]. Most studies have been performed with bottom-up produced particles. This means that, whilst great knowledge exists about interactions between bottom-up NPs and organisms, there is not enough research conducted about top-down plastics. The challenge primarily arises from the absence of standardised materials, which undermines data reliability and hampers the accurate quantification of NPs in the environment. Moreover, over 90% of toxicity studies concerning NPs have exclusively investigated PS or poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) [16–19].

Over the last years, various methods for producing NPs have been developed, based on grinding (e.g., with a ball mill), polymerisation, and precipitation. However, each technique exhibits challenges that hinder their ability to produce standardised NP particles [20].

Milling techniques have also been of use to produce NPs, ball milling and rotatory milling being the most used methods [21]. While the resulting fragments may resemble environmental NPs in morphology, their shapes are often complex and highly heterogeneous, making standardisation challenging [22, 23]. Additionally, contamination is a frequent concern due to the potential degradation of the balls used in the grinding process.

Laser ablation is another valuable technique to produce NPs [24–26]. Although it can generate NPs of approximately 30 nm, the technique has several drawbacks. Firstly, it requires specialised instruments that are typically costly. Additionally, the laser may provoke carbonisation, significantly altering the chemical composition of the particles and potentially increasing their toxicity. Another issue is the redeposition of ablation waste, enhancing the time needed to produce the desired quantity of nanoparticles. Lastly, some polymers exhibit low sensitivity to the radiation emitted by the laser [27, 28].

Polymer dissolution followed by precipitation is a rapid and economical method for producing nanoparticles. However, this technique has some drawbacks, including the use of solvents such as toluene, sodium hydroxide, or fluorosulfonic acid, often in combination with high temperatures [29, 30].

Sonication is the application of sound energy to agitate particles contained in a sample. This technique employs ultrasonic waves, typically in the range from 20 kHz to 1 MHz, to induce cavitation—the formation, growth, and implosive collapse of bubbles in a liquid. The collapse of these bubbles generates localised high temperature and pressure, leading to material fragmentation into smaller particles. Sonication approaches offer several advantages to produce NPs. Firstly, it is a relatively simple and cost-effective technique that can be easily implemented in laboratory settings. Secondly, the method allows for control of particle size and distribution by adjusting sonication parameters such as energy, amplitude, and frequency. Ultimately, sonication can be applied to a wide range of plastic materials, making it a versatile tool for generating NPs from various sources. To date, only a few studies have utilised this approach, even though they have shown promising results, including the successful production of nanoscale particles [31, 32].

This study aims to develop and optimize a sonication-assisted method for the production of true-to-life NPs from polymeric materials. The goal is to provide researchers with standardized NPs that closely mimic those found in the environment, enabling more accurate and representative studies on their behavior, toxicity, and environmental impact. This research is intended to support the scientific community in advancing our understanding of NPs and their implications for ecosystems and human health.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and devices

For NP production experiments, various materials were utilised, all sourced from used products. For instance, tyre wear (TW) from wheels, PET was obtained from bottles, PS were derived from foam, and LDPE from plastic bags. Additionally, a transparent cuvette, typically indicated for fluorescence or dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements, was employed for HDPS. Although HDPS is less common in the environment compared to

other plastics, it can be found in everyday items such as laboratory equipment, optical devices, and certain types of food packaging, making it relevant for studies on plastic degradation and nanoparticle release.

The milling step was conducted using a Pulverisette 14 (Fritsch, Pittsboro, USA), preceded by a liquid-nitrogen (Linde Group, Dublin, Ireland) mixing step together with the plastic material. For sonication, a Branson Branson[®] CPXH Digital Bath 5800 (Branson, Connecticut, USA) was employed, able to provide an acoustic power Pac (W) level in the range of 160 W, typically operating at a frequency between 40 and 45 kHz. Sample filtering was performed with disposable syringes and either 1 μm or 10 μm single-use acrylic copolymer (Acrodisc[®]) membrane filters (VWR Belgium). Ultra-pure water (18.2 M Ω cm) was dispensed from a Milli-Q system (Millipore, Burlington, MA, USA).

2.2. Protocol for NP degradation

To achieve degradation, polymers were first grinded to a size of approximately 1 mm using a variable speed Fritsch rotor mill under offline cryogenic conditions. Liquid nitrogen was added along with the plastic material to maintain these conditions, and after nitrogen evaporation the plastic-made sample was milled. Separate amounts of 250 mg for each grinded polymer were weighed in 20 ml glass vials and suspended in 2 ml of ultra-pure water. All analyses were performed in duplicate to ensure reproducibility and reliability of the results.

Samples were subjected to sonication in an ultrasound bath Branson Branson[®] CPXH 5800 ultrasound bath operating at a fixed frequency of 40 kHz. To prevent thermal degradation of the plastic nanoparticles, the bath temperature was maintained at 35 °C. The sonication procedure was optimised by systematically varying total applied ultrasonic energy, in order to achieve efficient nanoparticle release. Following sonication, the samples were filtered using a disposable syringe equipped with a 1 μm glass fibre filter, washed prior to use, and intended to both isolate the nanoparticles and minimise contamination. Specific experimental details will be reported in results section.

Glass vials filled with only 2 ml of ultra-pure water were used as blanks. Every experiment batch also comprised two procedural blanks submitted to the aforementioned protocol for plastic degradation under the same conditions.

2.3. Sizing and characterisation of produced nanoplastics

Size distribution for NPs obtained after the optimised procedure was gathered using DLS and nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA). Three replicates for each measurement were performed.

DLS acquisitions were conducted with a Zetasizer ZS (Malvern Panalytical, Worcestershire, UK). Measurements took place using a 4 mW He–Ne 633 nm laser module operating at 25 °C at an angle of 173° (back scattering), and results were treated using Malvern DTS 7.03 software. Only the samples with promising DLS results were analysed with NTA.

Measurements of particle concentration were acquired by a NTA Zetaview PMX-120 device (Malvern Panalytical, Worcestershire, UK). A dilution between 1:100 and 1:400 was carried out for the measured samples, as their particle concentration was initially unknown.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging was conducted for morphological characterisation of the NPs obtained. The SEM device of use was Nova NanoSEM450 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA). The microscope is equipped with a field emission gun (FEG). The images were gathered at a voltage of 5 kV and in back scattered mode. A droplet of the solution was air-dried on a Si-plate. A thin coating of 2.5 nm (Pt/Pd 80/20) was applied to the samples before they were introduced into the SEM.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optimisation of sonication parameters

The sonication-assisted method for the release of NPs from real-life polymeric materials, including PET, HDPS, LDPE, and TW, was systematically optimised in this study. The outcome highlighted that both total applied ultrasonic energy and the physical properties of the polymers were critical factors influencing the efficiency of NP production. Key properties such as crystallinity, molecular structure, density, and the presence of stabilising additives significantly affected the susceptibility of polymers to ultrasonic degradation [2, 3]. The optimisation was tailored to minimise thermal degradation and ensure consistency across different types of plastics. Noticeably, PET and TW samples exhibited significant NP release, whereas HDPS and LDPE showed limited degradation, suggesting that the polymer structure and the presence of stabilising additives may play a pivotal role in the sonication-assisted breakdown process.

Table 1. Ultrasonic energy (E) and energy density (E_ρ) figures for the sonication periods applied to the polymeric materials.

Sonication time (h)	E (kJ)	E_ρ (kJ ml ⁻¹)
4	2304	0.4
8	4608	0.9
16	9216	1.7
32	18432	3.5
48	27648	5.2
56	32256	6.1
64	36864	7.0

3.1.1. Total applied ultrasonic energy

The optimisation involved several experiments with several sonication periods, throughout which the ultrasonic energy was increasing. By applying equations (1) and (2)

$$E = P \cdot t \quad (1)$$

$$E_\rho = \frac{E}{V} \quad (2)$$

in which E is ultrasonic energy (J), P is power (W), t is sonication time (s), E_ρ is the energy density (kJ ml⁻¹) and V is volume (ml). The water volume filling the ultrasonic bath was fixed at 5.3 l. The different ultrasonic energy and energy density values were calculated. Table 1 shows figures corresponding to the increasing periods at 160 W, this being constant power value for the sonication device.

Firstly, energy density doses ranging from 0.4 to 5.2 kJ ml⁻¹ to ensure NP release from polymeric materials were applied. For TW samples, additional tests extended the applied energy density up to 6.1 and 7.0 kJ ml⁻¹ due to their complex composition, aiming to enhance the yield of nanoparticle production. It was observed that an extension of the total applied energy led to a higher yield of NPs. PET, a widely used plastic in consumer products, started to release detectable amounts of NPs after applying an energy density of 3.5 kJ ml⁻¹ (equivalent to 32 h at 160 W), as obtained DLS counts suggested and SEM imaging supported, with a maximum yield observed at 5.2 kJ ml⁻¹ (equivalent to 48 h at 160 W) (figure 1(A)) and consistent particle diameter between 200 and 300 nm (figure 1(B)). Further DLS parameters can be found in table S1. This trend aligns with previous studies by von der Esch *et al* [31], who reported similar degradation patterns in aquatic environments, indicating that prolonged mechanical stress is necessary to achieve significant fragmentation of PET-based materials. In contrast, TW required extended sonication of up to an energy density value of 7.0 kJ ml⁻¹, perhaps owing to filler components namely carbon black, which enhance mechanical durability but hinder degradation [14].

It is remarkable to point out that a low cutoff limit was established on the basis of a minimum scattering intensity rate value, with the aim of considering the reliability of DLS measurements. Given that procedural blanks provided intensity rate values from 1000 to 2000 kcps, it was determined that only measurements above 20000 kcps, 10 times higher than blank scattering, were of interest for an initial hypothesis about the presence of particles in the samples. To better illustrate the optimisation of total applied ultrasonic energy, SEM images of PET nanoparticles were collected after various sonication energy inputs. The SEM pictures revealed distinct morphological features depending on the applied energy. After applying an energy density of 5.2 kJ ml⁻¹ (equivalent to 48 h at 160 W) (figure 2), large, elongated, and spherical particles were observed, indicating an initial phase of mechanical breakdown where cavitation primarily produces irregular fragments. At this stage, the extended sonication period exerted higher mechanical stress on the polymer matrix, promoting additional fragmentation. Repeated cavitation events and surface reorganization facilitated the formation of more spherical particles, consistent with thermodynamic principles favoring a reduction in surface energy through morphologies with lower surface-to-volume ratios. Additionally, the images showed evidence of particle aggregation, with clusters formed by multiple smaller particles. To minimise potential artefacts from sample preparation, a droplet of NP suspension was air-dried on a silicon plate and coated with a thin layer of Pt/Pd (80/20) (2.5 nm) prior to SEM imaging. Despite these precautions, some degree of aggregation may still arise from the drying process. However, the presence of aggregates was also corroborated by DLS measurements in aqueous suspension, supporting the conclusion that aggregation occurred during sonication as a result of enhanced particle–particle interactions.

In evaluating the optimisation of total applied ultrasonic energy for TW samples, the initial sonication energy (equivalent to 40 h at 160 W) showed minimal degradation, indicating a high resistance of the material to ultrasonic breakdown (figure 3(A)). However, after extending the energy density up to 5.2 kJ ml⁻¹, a significant increase in nanoparticle release was observed. Correlograms for this occurrence are depicted in figure 3(B),

further DLS parameters being shown in table S2. This enhanced susceptibility to degradation was confirmed by NTA measurements, which indicated a mean nanoparticle diameter of approximately 151 nm, estimated particle concentration being in the region of $2 \times 10^9 \text{ particles ml}^{-1}$. The results suggest that applying sufficiently high total ultrasonic energy is crucial for overcoming the structural resilience exhibited by additives such as

Figure 3. Correlation between total applied ultrasonic energy to NP degradation from TW material: (A) average derived count rate by DLS; (B) correlograms obtained by DLS measurements in aqueous suspension for two independent sample replicates (three measurements each) at an energy density of 7.0 kJ ml⁻¹.

carbon black, which enhance the durability of TW material. SEM analysis further confirmed the polydispersity of the particles, showing a combination of spherical, irregular, and elongated shapes, as shown in figure 4.

For HDPS, the sonication procedure exhibited a different trend shown in figure 5(A), further DLS parameters being found in table S3. The scattering intensity rate, measured by DLS, steadily increased when energy density rose beyond 6.0 kJ ml⁻¹ (equivalent to 56 h at 160 W), indicating continuous fragmentation and release of nanoparticles. However, beyond this point, the count rate decreased, suggesting potential saturation of particle release or the onset of aggregation phenomena. Prior to DLS and NTA analysis, the samples were filtered through a 1- μ m glass fibre filter to remove larger aggregates and ensure accurate size distribution measurements. The DLS correlograms showed an average particle diameter lower than 300 nm (figure 5(B)), while NTA data indicated a smaller mean diameter range of 87 nm to 121 nm. These differences in size measurements between DLS and NTA may be attributed to the different detection principles of the techniques, where DLS tends to be influenced by larger aggregates, while NTA provides a more accurate representation of the smaller, dispersed nanoparticles.

3.1.2. Temperature

Maintaining a stable ultrasound bath temperature of 35 °C was essential to prevent thermal degradation of the polymers. Thermal effects during sonication can lead to polymer softening, melting or chemical modifications that may alter NP characteristics, thereby reducing efficiency of mechanical breakdown into NPs.

Figure 4. Relevant SEM images of released NPs from real-life TW material after an applied ultrasonic energy density of 6.1 kJ ml^{-1} (equivalent to 56 h at 160 W).

Figure 5. Correlation between total applied ultrasonic energy to NP degradation from HDPS material: (A) average derived count rate by DLS; (B) correlograms obtained by DLS measurements in aqueous suspension for a single sample (three measurements) at an energy density of 6.1 kJ ml^{-1} .

To maintain consistent thermal conditions, two different strategies were evaluated. The first approach involved hourly replacement of the bath water with fresh, temperature-equilibrated water. The second approach consisted of periodically adding ice to minimise water temperature increase. Table 2 shows DLS results for PET

Table 2. Relevant DLS parameters for sonication-assisted NP release from PET bottles after applying an energy density of 5.2 kJ ml^{-1} at two different cooling methods. Main conditions: Laser module: 4 mW He–Ne 633 nm; Operating temperature: $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; Back-scattering angle: 173° .

Cooling method	Mean particle diameter (nm)	PDI	Attenuator	Mean derived counts (kcps)
Water replacement	238.3 ± 6.2	0.213	5	114395.9 ± 2883.8
Ice addition	252.1 ± 1.4	0.266	6	69634.3 ± 10016.7

material at an applied energy density of 5.2 kJ ml^{-1} for each strategy. The main DLS parameters were similar for the suspensions obtained under the aforementioned strategies.

Even though the primary goal of ice addition was to maintain the appropriate temperature, the total water volume in the bath increased as a consequence of ice melting. This unexpected volume increase was assumed to alter the spatial distribution of ultrasonic waves and reduce the effective ultrasonic energy density (energy per unit volume), which in this setup was estimated to decrease to approximately $0.1\text{--}0.2 \text{ kJ ml}^{-1}$ (equivalent to 1–2 h of sonication at 160 W). Additionally, fluctuations in water level may lead to changes in acoustic impedance, affecting energy transfer from the transducer to the sample. These factors can be a reason behind the inconsistent mechanical stress applied to the polymer matrix.

Variations in water volume can lead to changes in acoustic impedance, affecting the energy transfer from the transducer to the sample and resulting in inconsistent mechanical stress applied to the polymer suspension. Despite efforts to control these variations, slight fluctuations persisted, possibly impacting the reproducibility of the sonication process, as both full immersion and stable positioning of sample vials are critical to ensure uniform ultrasonic wave transmission [33].

Nevertheless, both temperature control approaches yielded comparable qualitative results in nanoparticle analysis, suggesting that minor fluctuations in energy density and water level would not significantly impair NP generation under the tested conditions.

3.1.3. Filtration

In addition to optimising sonication parameters, refining the filtration step was crucial to ensure accurate size distribution analysis and prevent contamination during NP collection. Given the complexity of collecting sub-micrometre particles without introducing bias or losses, an efficient filtration protocol was necessary for obtaining reliable data on the size and concentration of NPs produced by sonication. A schematic representation of filtration procedure is depicted in figure 6.

The filtration step in this study involved a combination of disposable syringes and glass fibre filters of varying pore sizes. Initial tests employed $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ glass fibre filters (Acrodisc[®]) to remove larger debris and microplastics. Next, a secondary filtration step using $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ filters (Acrodisc[®]) was implemented to collect finer NP particles, aiming to reduce the presence of oversized contaminants and ensure a more homogenous NP sample, and suitable for DLS and NTA. The decision to employ a two-step filtration approach aligns with the methodology used in previous studies, such as those conducted by Tanaka *et al* [23], who highlighted the importance of sequential filtration to prevent clogging and enhance NP recovery efficiency.

Moreover, a backwashing step was tested as an additional action. After filtration through $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ filters, 2 ml of ultrapure water were passed through the opposite side of the $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ filter, pushing the liquid back through it. This backflow was aimed at detaching and loosening NPs previously stuck within the filter pores or its surface throughout sample filtration. The backwashed fluid was collected in a clean vial. Implementation of backwashing was intended to recover smaller nanoparticles, and potentially enhancing reliability of subsequent DLS and NTA measurements. Nevertheless, results discussed in this work corresponded to the double-filtration approach, as backwashing was not observed to provide better results.

Maintaining consistent filtration efficiency was further challenged by the presence of surfactants or additives in the polymer matrices. Mitrano *et al* [11] reported that these additives could affect the hydrophobicity of particles, potentially altering their interaction with filter media and resulting in reduced filtration efficiency or particle loss. The introduction of iterative washing steps before sample filtering was intended to circumvent this drawback, as well as to avoid the complete saturation of filters, potentially reducing the risk of particle aggregation and improving the consistency of NP recovery. The filtration protocol, involving a two-step sequential filtering, was selected and intended to ensure the accurate characterisation of NPs, with a clear size distribution consistent with environmentally relevant NPs, as supported by recent findings in environmental nanoparticle studies [11, 23]. Further research in this regard may help give a step forward in NP isolation, with an ultimate goal of improving reliability of current methodologies.

Figure 6. Overview of filtration approach employed in this study.

In addition, this methodology aligns with best practices for NP characterisation in environmental monitoring studies, as noted by Moon *et al* [14] and other recent research focusing on nanoparticle behaviour in complex matrices.

3.2. Influence of additives

The differences in NP release between polymers can be largely attributed to the stabilising additives present in the material. Additives such as plasticisers, UV stabilisers, and flame retardants increase material resistance to mechanical stress and environmental degradation. For instance, LDPE and PS contain additives that enhance flexibility and durability, making them more resistant to breakdown under ultrasonic cavitation. Mitrano *et al* [11] highlighted that these additives reduce polymer chain mobility, making cavitation-induced scission less effective, as observed in LDPE samples (figure 7, table S4), where negligible NP release occurred even after 64 h of sonication.

Even though PET and TW may also contain similar additives, the sonication-assisted approach in this work showed an efficient particle release from these materials. PET may be more sensitive to hydrolytic and mechanical degradation, particularly in its amorphous regions. Tyre materials are complex composites

Table 3. Relevant DLS parameters for sonication-assisted NP release from PET bottles subject to centrifugal and ball milling. Main conditions: Laser module: 4 mW He–Ne 633 nm; Operating temperature: 25 °C; Back-scattering angle: 173°.

Material	Mean particle diameter (nm)	PDI	Attenuator	Mean derived counts (kcps)
PET sample 1	200.3 ± 8.2	0.283	10	1176.9 ± 7.5
PET sample 2	263.0 ± 104.6	0.397	10	416.0 ± 11.1

including vulcanisation agents and fillers such as carbon black, which may confer a different degradation behaviour under sonication. These findings support the hypothesis that the interplay between polymer composition, additives, and sonication parameters determines the extent of NP release. The occurrence of cavitation, characterised by the formation, growth, and implosive collapse of microbubbles, generates localised high values of temperature and pressure, leading to polymer chain scission. This mechanical action, as observed by Tanaka *et al* [23], was crucial for fragmenting PE and PS chains under sonication.

3.3. Comparison with alternative degradation methods

The sonication-assisted method was considered to possess advantages over traditional mechanical and chemical degradation approaches. Ball milling, a commonly used method for NP production, often results in a wide range of particle sizes and potential contamination from the milling media. Lionetto *et al* [21] reported that ball milling introduces metal particles from the milling balls, leading to potential contamination, whereas sonication, lacking direct abrasive contact, minimises this risk. Prior to opting for the approach described in this work, the aforementioned research had been considered in the laboratory as an initial strategy. In a similar way, the procedure involved ultra centrifugal and ball milling, followed by powder collection, resuspension in water and filtration. Table 3 summarises relevant DLS parameters for the NPs obtained after carrying out this procedure.

In the light of these results, even though it may be hypothesised that NP production was occurring, the low mean derived count and the high attenuator value were considered as indicators of transparent solutions, thus not containing particles. Moreover, the variability between samples was noticeable, and it was decided not to proceed with this approach.

Alternative techniques such as laser ablation and solvent precipitation also present limitations. Laser ablation requires a significant energy input and can lead to material carbonisation, altering nanoparticles chemical composition. Sorensen *et al* [28] emphasised that carbonisation provoked by laser treatment may increase toxicity of the produced particles, while solvent-based methods pose environmental and health risks due to the use of hazardous chemicals [30]. When compared with the above methods, sonication was hypothesised to offer a safer, environmentally friendly approach, applicable to a broader range of polymeric materials, potentially providing a versatile solution for NP production from various plastic sources.

Table 4. Relevant DLS parameters for sonication-assisted NP release from PET bottles and particle concentration determined by NTA. Main conditions: Laser module: 4 mW He–Ne 633 nm; Operating temperature: 25 °C; Back-scattering angle: 173°.

Material	Mean particle diameter (nm)	PDI	Attenuator	Mean derived counts (kcps)	Particle concentration (particles ml ⁻¹)
PET sample 1	284.5 ± 18.8	0.309	7	26272.4 ± 608.4	2.2 × 10 ⁹
PET sample 2	325.3 ± 30.4	0.343	7	29739.1 ± 289.8	2.5 × 10 ⁹

3.4. Characterisation and environmental relevance of nanoplastics

The hydrodynamic diameters for PET-derived NPs ranged from 150 to 350 nm, while TW-derived NPs happened to be smaller, between 87 and 150 nm. These sizes are ecologically relevant, as NPs in this size region are readily absorbed by aquatic organisms, possibly entering the food chain. Mitrano *et al* [11] and Gopinath *et al* [12] reported enhanced cellular uptake and bioaccumulation of NPs in this size range, highlighting their potential ecological risks.

The heterogeneity shown in above SEM images is advantageous for environmental studies, as it represents the diversity of particles encountered in natural ecosystems, aligning with observations carried out by Tanaka *et al* [23] of true-to-life environmental NPs produced throughout natural weathering processes.

The successful production of NPs using this sonication-assisted method holds significant implications for environmental monitoring and risk assessment. By providing a reproducible approach to generating NPs from common plastics, this method enables more realistic studies on their behaviour, transport, and interactions with biota in aquatic environments. It bridges the gap between synthetic bottom-up NPs and true-to-life top-down NPs observed in nature, as highlighted by Zhang *et al* [13].

3.5. Methodology verification

To ensure the reliability and reproducibility of the sonication-assisted NP production method, replication experiments took place in the same laboratory with a different analyst. The experimental procedure was similar to above conditions, and performed in separate days to achieve extended total applied ultrasonic energy. The setup maintained consistent sample preparation and particle size analysis techniques, with an applied ultrasonic energy density of 7.0 kJ ml⁻¹ to maximize release of NP from polymeric material. Hydrodynamic diameters and particle concentrations were analyzed using DLS and NTA to assess the repeatability of the results.

The verification experiment utilized the same amount (around 250 mg) of cryogenically milled powder derived from PET bottles, TW, LDPE from plastic bags, and HDPS cuvettes. The extended total applied ultrasonic energy yielded a satisfying NP release for PET bottles, whilst the rest of materials would show no particle release. As demonstrated in table 4, measurements performed by DLS revealed an average hydrodynamic diameter in the region of 300 nm for PET-derived NPs, as scattering intensity rate was greater than 20,000 kcps, attenuator value was 7 and polydispersity index fell in the region of 0.3, these being indicators of efficient NP release. Correlograms for these measurements are exhibited in figure 8, and further DLS parameters can be found in table S5. Moreover, NTA measurements estimated that particle concentration was in the region of 2 × 10⁹ particles ml⁻¹.

Morphological characterization via SEM demonstrated a diverse population of nanoparticles (figure 9), including spherical and irregularly shaped particles, closely resembling environmentally relevant top-down nanoparticles. These observations permit to validate method effectiveness for NP release under replicated conditions, with consistent and reproducible outcome achieved across different experimental runs, as previously exhibited by DLS figures.

Interestingly, the extended total applied ultrasonic energy density of 7.0 kJ ml⁻¹ appeared to be critical for PET material, potentially due to its semi-crystalline polymer structure, which was hypothesised to require prolonged mechanical stress to facilitate chain scission and subsequent particle release. PET crystalline regions may offer higher resistance to cavitation-induced fragmentation compared to its amorphous regions. The prolonged exposure ensured sufficient energy transfer to overcome these crystalline domains, resulting in enhanced NP production.

In contrast, materials such as TW, LDPE, and HDPS exhibited limited nanoparticle release, potentially due to their complex additive compositions or highly flexible polymer chains, which reduce susceptibility to ultrasonic degradation. This suggests that additional methodological adjustments, such as chemical or enzymatic pre-treatment, may be necessary to optimise nanoparticle production for these polymers.

These findings underscore the reliability of the sonication-assisted method for producing environmentally relevant PET nanoparticles, meeting key requirements for environmental and toxicological studies. The particle size of 300 nm and the high particle concentration achieved indicate that this approach holds promise as a standardized procedure for PET nanoparticle release from bottles. This approach may also tackle recent

environmental concerns on metals, namely titanium, that are present as additives in the composition of opaque PET bottles [34]. Apart from their potential toxicological profile, the gathering of titanium-doped NPs may constitute a reliable true-to-life model to follow up their fate in complex matrices, including experimental *in vivo* models.

4. Conclusions

In this study, a simple and effective size reduction procedure was developed to prepare PET and TW NPs from real-life polymeric material. Understanding the sonication step was crucial for selecting the appropriate procedural conditions to achieve nanometric dispersions of the target NPs in water. The optimised procedure involved an initial cryogenic mill, followed by an applied ultrasonic energy density of 5.2 kJ ml⁻¹ for PET (equivalent to 48 h at 160 W) and 7.0 kJ ml⁻¹ for TW (equivalent to 64 h at 160 W). Images by SEM confirmed that the produced particles did not exhibit a uniform shape, indicating that the sonicated-assisted method effectively released actual NPs. The primary advantage of this method is its ability to produce PET and TW dispersions in water in a shorter time period than other methods reported in literature. Additionally, the method favoured a polydisperse size distribution, facilitating size-based separation for further studies on interactions between NPs and marine organisms. This method is straightforward, requiring no special laboratory equipment, water temperature being the only critical parameter to monitor in the ultrasound bath. Moreover, the lack of contact between plastic material and surfaces such as mill balls significantly reduced the risk of

contamination. The proposed method opens the possibility of future research combining this technique with grinding or centrifugation. A combined approach may be of use for plastic materials namely HDPS, LDPE and PS, herein not shown to be prone to sonication-assisted degradation.

Future research shall be focused on optimising sonication parameters across different polymer types and exploring the effects of varying environmental conditions, such as salinity, pH, and temperature, on NP release. Additionally, integrating sonication with chemical or enzymatic treatment could enhance the degradation efficiency of more resistant polymers namely LDPE and PS, thus expanding the method applicability for comprehensive environmental risk assessment.

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Conflict of interest statement

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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